

Reaction of 2-Aminothiophenol with some Ketones of Stigmastane Series

M. MUSHFIQ* and G. MUDGAL

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

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In continuation of our earlier work on steroidal benzothiazepine¹ we have now carried out the reactions of α,β -unsaturated ketones of stigmastane series, viz. 6-oxostigmast-4-en-3 β -yl acetate (1), its 3 β -propionate analogue (2) and 3,6-dioxostigmast-4-ene (3) with 2-aminothiophenol². 1 and 2 provided the [4 $\alpha,6bc$]benzothiazepine-3 β -yl acetate (4) and its β -propionate derivative (5). The half band width (17 Hz) of the C3-proton at δ 5.05 in the nmr spectrum of 4 suggests that it is axial in nature thus rendering the A/B ring junction as *trans*³. The multiplet at δ 2.8 ($W_{1/2}$ 10 Hz) for C4-proton can be rationalised better if we consider it to be β -oriented (axial)³ and hence the sulphur as α -oriented. The Drieding models also support this stereochemical assignment.

In the reaction of 3 with 2-aminothiophenol there are two possibilities where the reagent can incorporate, either on 3,5-position or on 4,6-position. The 4,6-benzothiazepine (6) has less strain in the Drieding model as compared to the strain in 3,5-benzothiazepine (7) in the model. The two signals each for one proton at δ 5.6 and 3.0 as

distorted doublet and multiplet can also be attributed to C4- and C5-protons respectively, if we consider the structure 6 in preference over 7.

NOTES

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

A mixture of ketone (2 g) and 2-aminothiophenol (0.49 g) in absolute methanol (40 ml) having concentrated HCl (2 drops) was refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 5 h, then cooled and the separated solid was recrystallised from methanol. However, in case of **3** the usual work up afforded **6** as an oil which was purified by silica gel column chromatography.

1 gave **4** (0.98 g), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 76.6; H, 9.5; N, 2.4. $C_{37}H_{55}NSO_2$ requires: C, 76.89; H, 9.59; N, 2.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 065, 1 645 (aromatic), 1 740, 1 245 (acetate), 1 580 (C=N) and 740 cm^{-1} (C-S); pmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.1 (2H, m, C6''-H, C9''-H), 6.7 (2H, m, C7''-H, C8''-H), 5.05 (1H, m, C3 α -H, $W_{1,2}$ 17 Hz), 2.8 (1H, m, C4-H, $W_{1,2}$ 10 Hz), 2.4 (3H, m, C5-H, C7-H₂), 2.0 (3H, s, CH_3COO), 1.0, 0.9, 0.8, 0.75 and 0.7 (6 $\times$ Me).

2 provided **5** (0.85 g), m.p. 196° (Found: C, 77.1; H, 9.7; N, 2.3. $C_{38}H_{57}NSO_2$ requires: C, 77.10; H, 9.1; N, 2.37%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 065, 1 650 (aromatic), 1 735 (C_2H_5COO), 1 580 (C=N) and 740 cm^{-1} (C-S); pmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.1 (2H, m, C6''-H, C9''-H), 6.8 (2H, m, C7''-H, C8''-H), 4.8 (1H, m, C3 α -H, $W_{1,2}$ 14 Hz), 3.1 (1H, m, C4 β -H),

2.45_i (3H, m, C5-H, C7-H₂), 2.32 (2H, q, CH_3-CH_2COO), 1.17 (3H, t, CH_3CH_2COO), 1.02, 0.98, 0.85, 0.78 and 0.69 (6 $\times$ Me).

3 afforded **6** (0.75 g), oil (Found: C, 78.7; H, 9.6; N, 2.6. $C_{35}H_{51}NSO_2$ requires: C, 78.74; H, 9.63; N, 2.62%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 000, 1 620 (aromatic), 1 705 (C=O), 1 582 (C=N) and 755 cm^{-1} (C-S); pmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 6.4 (4H, m, ArH), 5.6 (1H, d, C4-H), 3.0 (1H, m, C5-H), 2.1 (4H, m, C2-H₂, C7-H₂), 1.1, 1.0, 0.95, 0.8 and 0.7 (6 $\times$ Me).

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